

40 years of Joint Venture in Brazil: How Regional Partnerships Boosted Economic Sectors

*40 anos de Joint Venture no Brasil: Como Parcerias Regionais
Impulsionaram Setores Econômicos*

*40 años de Joint Venture en Brasil: Cómo las Alianzas Regionales
Impulsaron Sectores Económicos*

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Abstract:

This article discusses the historical origin and concept of joint ventures, highlighting their evolution from ancient business practices to their contemporary application in globalization. A joint venture is defined as a collaboration between companies to seek economic benefits, expand or diversify, and may involve the creation of a new entity with different ownership structures. Reasons for forming a joint venture include technological acquisition, knowledge assimilation, market expansion and overcoming financial challenges. Strategic advantages stand out, including resource sharing, access to new markets, economies of scale, production efficiency, technology transfer, and portfolio diversification. Nonetheless, disadvantages are also discussed, for instance the time and resources required to establish and manage the joint venture, as well as potential conflicts of interest.

Keywords: *Joint Venture; Strategic Collaboration; Business Motivation.*

Resumo:

O artigo aborda a origem histórica e o conceito de joint ventures, destacando sua evolução desde práticas comerciais antigas até sua aplicação contemporânea na globalização. A joint venture é definida como uma colaboração entre empresas para buscar benefícios econômicos, expandir-se ou diversificar, podendo envolver a criação de uma nova entidade com diferentes estruturas de participação. Os motivos para formar uma joint venture incluem aquisição de tecnologia, assimilação de conhecimento, expansão de mercado e superação de desafios financeiros. Destacam-se as vantagens estratégicas, como compartilhamento de recursos, acesso a novos mercados, economia de escala, eficiência na produção, transferência de tecnologia e diversificação do portfólio. No entanto, são discutidas também desvantagens, como o tempo e recursos necessários para iniciar e administrar a joint venture, além dos conflitos de interesses.

Recebido

Received

Recibido

Dezembro, 2024

December, 2024

Diciembre, 2024

Aceito

Accepted

Aceptado

Maio, 2025

May, 2025

Mayo, 2025

Publicado

Published

Publicado

Junho, 2025

June, 2025

Junio, 2025

<https://git.fateczl.edu.br>

e_ISSN

2965-3339

DOI

10.29327/2384439.3.3-5

São Paulo

v. 3 | n. 3

v. 3 | i. 3

e33351

Abril-Junho

April-June

Abril-Junio

2025

Palavras-chave: Joint Venture; Colaboração Estratégica; Motivações Empresariais.

Resumen:

El artículo aborda el origen histórico y el concepto de las joint ventures, destacando su evolución desde prácticas comerciales antiguas hasta su aplicación contemporánea en la globalización. Una joint venture se define como una colaboración entre empresas para buscar beneficios económicos, expandirse o diversificarse, pudiendo implicar la creación de una nueva entidad con diferentes estructuras de participación. Los motivos para formar una joint venture incluyen la adquisición de tecnología, la asimilación de conocimientos, la expansión del mercado y la superación de desafíos financieros. Se destacan las ventajas estratégicas, como el intercambio de recursos, el acceso a nuevos mercados, las economías de escala, la eficiencia en la producción, la transferencia de tecnología y la diversificación del portafolio. Sin embargo, también se discuten desventajas, como el tiempo y los recursos necesarios para iniciar y administrar la joint venture, además de los conflictos de intereses potenciales.

Palabras clave: Joint Venture; Colaboración Estratégica; Motivaciones Empresariales.

1. INTRODUCTION

Collaboration between companies through joint ventures has long been a strategy for seeking advantages. Theories of transaction costs, strategic behavior, and organizational learning are commonly used to explain companies' joint venture activities. Transaction cost explanations emphasize profit maximization using organizational form to minimize costs. Strategic behavior theorists explain the formation of joint ventures as stemming from companies' desire to increase profitability and, consequently, asset values through strategic moves against competitors. Organizational learning theory distinguishes between knowledge possessed by individuals and knowledge intrinsic to organizations.

There are many economic and strategic motivations for forming joint ventures. Joint ventures can create economies of scale, produce cost savings, create synergism with the partner or the parent company's own operations, and diversify the company into new product markets. Furthermore, an international joint venture can enable the company to enter new geographic markets effectively, present a local image in what would otherwise be a foreign market, satisfy provincial ownership or content requirements, and reduce exposure to the country risk inherent in single-company international ventures.

Given this scenario, the research question is: how have joint ventures in Brazil, from the 1980s to 2023, influenced the economic and strategic performance of the companies involved, especially concerning innovation and competitiveness in the global market? The general objective of this study is to analyze the evolution of joint ventures in Brazil over this period, with the aim of understanding their impact on innovation, competitiveness, and the strategic positioning of companies in the international context.

The strategic choice of establishing joint ventures has become an increasingly common practice in the contemporary business landscape. Given this trend, we seek to understand how joint ventures influence not only the internal dynamics of companies but also their positioning in the global market. This research aims to investigate the impact of joint ventures, with a particular focus on their relationship with the innovation and competitiveness of the companies that establish them.

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

2.1 Origin of Joint Ventures

Joint ventures have emerged gradually throughout history, with origins dating back to ancient commercial practices and specific contracts. Their concept developed progressively, rather than being instituted ad hoc (FALCONE, 2013). Traditionally, in the English legal context, they were associated with a "joint venture," often linked to navigation rights contracts, aimed at obtaining profits through overseas commercial activities, e.g. exports and imports (MIRANDA; MALUF, 2009).

The term "joint ventures" was introduced in Great Britain in the sixteenth century

and was used to describe partnerships that aimed to supply ships and conduct business overseas. These partnerships were, therefore, temporary and informal associations that played a role in the maritime trade of the time (ALMEIDA, 1987).

It is important to note that joint ventures are not creations of national legislators; they emerged from private practices, incorporation contracts and commercial activities (BASSO, 2002).

In the late 19th century, joint ventures began to be established, primarily in the form of partnerships, in the railway sector. Their purpose was to build shared stations and acquire carriages for use on railway lines. This collaborative model proved effective, and in the 20th century, joint ventures expanded to other sectors, such as the oil industry. In this context, joint research and development became the primary focus. This trend of resource concentration later extended to the steel industry, playing a significant role in the development of that sector (MIRANDA; MALUF, 2009).

Currently, amid globalization, joint ventures are emerging as an attractive option to meet the demands of an increasingly competitive and globalized market. They offer the opportunity to share technical knowledge that can be applied across a wide variety of sectors (MARQUES, 2016).

2.2 Joint Venture Concept

Rasmussen (1998) describes a joint venture as a "merger of interests" involving the collaboration of companies, economic groups, legal entities, or individuals. This collaboration is driven by the explicit pursuit of profits or benefits, whether for expansion or diversification, with the possibility of permanent or limited duration. This definition emphasizes the economic motivation behind joint ventures and their capacity to accommodate diverse time horizons.

According to Kotabe and Helsen (2000), a joint venture involves the creation of a new entity by two or more existing companies, with varying ownership structures, including majority, half-and-half, or minority ownership. These partnerships can be established for economic or political reasons, enabling foreign companies to collaborate with local partners to overcome financial, management, or resource challenges.

Schoppe (2008) describes them as "mechanisms of cooperation between companies" that are associative in nature, characterized by the sharing of resources and risks. These partnerships can have limited or unlimited objectives and duration, making them flexible and adaptable to the needs of the parties involved.

Bittar (1994) adds to the discussion, describing a joint venture as an "arrangement" designed to combine resources, techniques, and even technology transfer between different companies. This combination may or may not result in the creation of a new legal entity. These partnerships are characterized by equity participation, capital pooling, and the pursuit of a relationship that gradually evolves, progressing from mere equity participation to deeper entrepreneurial involvement.

Gherzi (1998) highlights the contractual nature of joint ventures, describing them as "contracts" in which multiple parties, both national and international, contribute diverse resources without losing their identity and individuality as legal entities or companies. These collaborations aim to undertake a joint business venture, which can range from the creation of goods to the provision of services, with a duration that may be limited. The ultimate goal is to obtain economic or financial benefits or increase equity value.

Eiriz (2001) emphasizes that joint ventures are strategic alliances focused on the financial aspect, as they involve the acceptance of capital for the shareholding structure of the newly created entity. These alliances are frequently formed in pursuit of commercial or production objectives, reflecting the search for economic advantages through cooperation.

Keegan and Green (1999) highlight the importance of joint ventures as a way to participate more extensively in foreign markets than simply exporting or licensing. These partnerships enable partners to leverage their distinct strengths within the value chain, including marketing, internationalization, and manufacturing capacity.

Noonam (1999) notes that some companies establish foreign subsidiaries or joint ventures to gain greater control over sales, distribution, manufacturing, and packaging operations. Both forms of partnership must comply with the laws of the country in which they are established.

Barney and Hesterly (2011) highlight another aspect of joint ventures, emphasizing that creating a separate legal entity in which partners invest and from which profits are earned can reduce the risk of cheating in strategic alliances. This is because, by cheating or acting deceitfully, a businessperson would be harming not only the partner companies but also his or her own company, with the potential for diminished profits due to such dishonest actions.

Furthermore, equity participation in joint ventures generally involves partners making equal contributions to the operations (HITT; HOSKISSON; IRELAND, 2008). Typically, partners contribute the same proportion of capital to the project, which is particularly common when only two companies are involved, resulting in a 50/50 split. However, there are cases where equity stakes can be diversified, and in these cases, profit sharing is proportional to the capital invested. This means that companies that invested more capital generally receive a larger share of the profits. Hence, joint ventures enable an equitable distribution of risks and a pooling of effort; although, the willingness of the parties involved is crucial to the success of this complex partnership.

2.3 Reasons for forming a joint venture

Hyder (1999) emphasized the importance of investigating the reasons that led to the formation of a joint venture to gain a comprehensive understanding of it. This involves analyzing the underlying reasons that led the partners to establish this partnership. These reasons, which may include technology acquisition, knowledge assimilation, and market expansion, play a crucial role in all stages of the joint venture formation process.

According to the research, we found that Brazilian companies are motivated to form international joint ventures for several reasons. Among these reasons are the pursuit of technology acquisition, the desire to gain competitive advantages over local competitors, and the exploitation of benefits associated with technological ownership, patents, and consolidation in the global market (OLIVEIRA; DRUMMOND; RODRIGUES, 1999). On the other hand, foreign partners are motivated by the prospect of increasing their profitability by leveraging managerial and technological capabilities, as well as access to established marketing channels, market knowledge, and an understanding of local legislation and administrative practices. According to the observations of Inkpen and Beamish (1997), access to local knowledge is essential for dealing with uncertainty and establishing an operational presence in a foreign country. They argue that international joint ventures offer an efficient and cost-effective way to quickly access new markets by leveraging the established partner's infrastructure.

Fey and Beamish (2001) observed that competitive pressures also drive companies to expand internationally, seeking economies of scale and scope. A wholly owned subsidiary could solve this problem. Even though, the choice of joint venture could be explained by the existence of cultural and institutional barriers.

Companies often choose to form joint ventures as a strategy to facilitate their entry into new international markets. By partnering with established local or foreign companies, they can leverage their market knowledge, existing infrastructure, and established business relationships, allowing them to expand their operations more easily and efficiently. This type of collaboration helps companies overcome initial barriers, for example regulatory and cultural issues, while sharing risks and costs, facilitating their internationalization and achieving a global presence (VILLELA, 2008).

2.4 Reasons for forming a joint venture

Forming a joint venture offers several strategic advantages for companies seeking to collaborate on joint projects and ventures. These advantages include the sharing of resources and risks, as mentioned by Schoppe (2008), allowing them to access knowledge, assets, and capabilities that they might not have individually. Furthermore, joint ventures provide access to new markets (INKPEN; BEAMISH, 1997), especially when a local company possesses valuable market knowledge and a foreign partner wishes to expand globally.

This collaboration also yields economies of scale and operational efficiency, resulting in reduced costs and more competitive prices (VILLELA, 2008). According to Ferraz (2001), technology transfer between partner companies is another significant advantage, driving innovation and enhancing the quality of products and services offered. Furthermore, joint ventures enable the sharing of knowledge and experience, which is essential for business growth and development.

A joint venture reduces risks by facing challenges with greater resilience, especially in unfamiliar or volatile markets. Start-up costs are generally lower because multiple parties share the expenses, making entry into new markets or the creation of new businesses more affordable. Local companies offer access to extensive local distribution channels, enhancing the marketing of products and services. Furthermore, flexibility and agility enable joint ventures to adapt quickly to changing market conditions (MILGATE, 2001).

Finally, Doz and Hamel (2000) point to portfolio diversification as another advantage, as joint ventures allow companies to explore new growth opportunities.

Regarding disadvantages, the process of starting operations and managing a joint venture generally requires more time and resources, which can be problematic for the parties involved (LE PERA, 1984). Furthermore, conflicts of interest often arise in contracts related to sales, purchasing, distribution, services, licensing, and other areas, which can negatively affect the effectiveness of the partnership.

Another significant challenge is the need to adapt to the national cultures and business practices of partner companies. Harmonizing different cultural approaches and operating methods can be complicated and time-consuming (CARVALHO, 2003). This can lead to internal conflicts and disagreements between the parties.

Furthermore, creating a joint venture can reduce flexibility in decision-making. When multiple parties are involved in decision-making, bureaucracy and approval processes can become more complex, which can impact on the company's agility in responding to changes in the business environment (DOZ; HAMEL, 2000).

3. METHOD

The methodology employed in the development of the article was based on bibliographic, exploratory, and descriptive research. Data were collected between August and October 2024 from articles, journals, and websites.

The bibliographic research covers all bibliography already made public in relation to the topic studied, from individual publications, bulletins, newspapers, magazines, books, research, monographs, theses, cartographic materials, Lakatos and Marconi (2001).

Exploratory research is usually small-scale and undertaken to define the exact nature of a problem and gain a better understanding of the environment in which it is occurring (MCDANIEL; RYLANDER, 2003).

Descriptive research uses a set of scientific methods and procedures to collect raw data and create a data structure that describes the existing characteristics of a defined target population (SAUNDERS; LEWIS; THORNHILL, 2010).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For a better illustration of the aspects covered in this study of joint ventures, below we present a series of graphs that provide a detailed analysis of mergers from the 1980s to 2023. The research, conducted between August and October 2024, allowed us to analyze and map the percentage of joint ventures existing in Brazil, also highlighting the main sectors present in each region of the country.

Chart 1 – Performance of Joint Ventures in Brazilian regions

Source: Authors (2024)

The performance of Brazil's regions, as shown in the graph below, indicates that the Southeast region has the highest percentage, at 31.8%. In second and third place, the North and South regions are tied, both with 21.2%, highlighting the importance of these regions. The Central-West region contributes approximately 13.6%, driven by the agricultural sector. Finally, the Northeast region has the lowest share, at 12.1%, which may be related to its lower level of industrialization compared to the other regions.

According to the sectoral breakdown for the Southeast region, the energy sector leads with approximately 25%, highlighting the importance of electricity and renewable energy. Next, the automotive sector accounts for 20%, reflecting the presence of automakers and auto parts manufacturers in the region. Infrastructure, pulp and paper, oil, and the banking sector each contribute approximately 10%. Other sectors, namely telecommunications, aviation, and consumer goods, have a smaller share, at 5% each.

Chart 2 – Sectoral Division of Joint Ventures in the Southeast Region

Source: Authors (2024)

Chart 3 – Sectoral Division of Joint Ventures in the Southern Region

Source: Authors (2024)

Regarding the sectoral breakdown of the Southern region of Brazil, the automotive sector leads with 21.4%, reflecting the presence of major automakers in the region. In second place, the steel sector represents 14.3%, driven by technological advancements and improvements in production. The other sectors, including food, media, beverages, sanitation, agribusiness, pulp and paper, renewable energy, home appliances, and industrial equipment, are tied, each with a 7.1% share.

Chart 4 – Sectoral Division of Joint Ventures in the Northern Region

Source: Authors (2024)

In the Brazilian North, given the region's geographic and economic context, which is rich in mineral resources and has significant energy potential, the presence of joint ventures is predominantly in the mining and energy sectors, both of which account for 35.7%. Next in line are mining and metallurgy, with 14.3%, and oil and gas, also with 14.3%, reflecting the region's strong dependence on natural resource extraction and industrial transformation.

Chart 5 – Sectoral Division of Joint Ventures in the Northeast Region

Source: Authors (2024)

In the Northeast region, most joint ventures are concentrated in the electric power sector, accounting for 25%, which may be related to the development of renewable energy sources, for instance wind power, which is widely explored in the region. Other sectors, including healthcare, chemicals and petrochemicals, steel, retail, natural gas, and pulp and paper, are equally represented, with 12.5% each, indicating a greater diversification of joint ventures across different sectors.

Chart 6 – Sectoral Division of Joint Ventures in the Central-West Region

Source: Authors (2024)

In the Central-West region, joint ventures stand out mainly in the energy and mining sectors, both with 22.2%. These sectors are relevant due to the growth of agribusiness and the need for energy infrastructure to support this expansion. Furthermore, the aerospace sector, with 11.1%, is also represented, demonstrating the region's development of aerospace technologies. Agribusiness and energy (biofuels) continue with equal participation, also representing 11.1% each.

Each graph was created to highlight the geographic concentration and sectoral diversity of joint ventures. By analyzing this data, we can identify regional and sectoral patterns that are crucial to understanding the effectiveness and potential of joint ventures in Brazil. The graph legend provides specific information about the sectors present in each region, allowing for a more precise and segmented analysis. This data is essential for formulating development strategies and potential investments that meet the characteristics of each region and sector.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Between the 1980s and 2023, joint ventures in Brazil played a crucial role in the expansion and diversification of the Brazilian economy. In the 1980s, with the gradual opening of the economy and the need for modernization, many foreign companies began forming joint ventures with local companies to enter the Brazilian market, taking advantage of tax and regulatory advantages.

Joint ventures remain an effective strategy for both foreign and Brazilian companies seeking to share risks, expand their operations, and enter new markets. With the growing importance of innovation and sustainability, many of these partnerships have focused on emerging sectors, including technology, renewable energy, and agribusiness. Brazil, as one of Latin America's largest consumer markets, continues to attract international investment. Joint ventures are seen as a path for the internationalization of Brazilian companies and the expansion of multinationals' presence in the country.

Between August and October, a survey was conducted to identify companies that had formed joint ventures in Brazil, to map the primary sectors that stood out from this type of partnership. The results revealed that sectors, for instance electric power, mining, and automotive were the primary beneficiaries.

The mining industry, particularly in the north of the country, gained prominence due to the presence of large mineral reserves, e.g. iron ore and bauxite, attracting international companies to form partnerships with Brazilian companies. One important player was Vale, which established several partnerships, expanding its market presence.

In Southern Brazil, the automotive sector stands out for its formation of joint ventures, driven by the region's strategic location and industrial heritage. A notable example is the partnership between Brazilian and foreign automakers, which seeks technological innovation and production efficiency, focusing on more sustainable and competitive vehicles for the global market.

While many of these partnerships were successful, some were discontinued due to market shifts or internal strategic changes. However, several remain active, consolidating themselves as important components in their respective markets.

We conclude that joint ventures have evolved from a solution to economic and market challenges in the 1980s to a strategic tool for growth and innovation, remaining relevant in Brazil's economic environment. They continue to shape crucial sectors of the economy, promoting competitiveness for both Brazilian and foreign companies.

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